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STRENGTH 2024

**STRENGTHENING SUSTAINABILITY COMMUNICATION IN TOURISM,
HOSPITALITY, AND EVEN INDUSTRIES**

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Book of Abstracts

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Novi Sad, August 2024

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STRENGTHENING SUSTAINABILITY COMMUNICATION IN TOURISM, HOSPITALITY, AND
EVEN INDUSTRIES

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Addressing Artificial Intelligence Bias in Accessible Smart Tourism for Sustainable Development

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Abstract: This paper delves into the pervasive issue of algorithmic bias within Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications, particularly as it pertains to the dynamic field of accessible smart tourism. With the tourism industry increasingly incorporating AI technologies into its operations, there has been a notable enhancement in efficiency and effectiveness. However, this surge in AI adoption has also brought to the forefront the challenge of bias, which poses significant hurdles for both tourists and tourism providers.

To dissect this complex problem, the presentation utilizes illustrative scenarios to shed light on various instances of AI bias within the tourism and hospitality sector. Additionally, it introduces a framework designed to assess the global implications of bias within the realms of smart tourism for sustainable development.

The presentation underscores the potential ramifications of bias on tourist experiences across different phases: pre-travel, during travel/on-site, and post-travel, while considering viewpoints from both tourists and providers. It emphasizes that many biases originate from the utilization of AI within online platforms, thereby impacting tourists' information retrieval, decision-making processes, and the marketing strategies employed by tourism providers. Furthermore, it delves into the broader effects of AI on tourist experiences, outlining the social implications, managerial considerations, and technological implications.

This presentation represents a pioneering effort in addressing the issue of AI bias within the context of smart tourism. Moreover, it lays out pathways for future research, spanning topics such as technology adoption and consumer behavior, the economic repercussions for tourism providers, sustainable development and the regulatory landscape.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Bias, Machine Learning, Smart Tourism, Accessibility, Sustainable Development.

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